

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 2.1 Recommendations on CCUS R&I priorities for Horizon Europe work programme

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordinated and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Contact details:

+32 2 882 50 07

iwg9@zeroemissionsplatform.eu

www.ccus-setplan.eu

www.zeroemissionsplatform.eu

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction.....	4
1.1	Background.....	4
2	The importance of CCS and CCU technologies and R&I.....	5
3	Key R&I solutions to support CCS/CCU deployment and scale up.....	6
3.1	CO2 Capture	6
3.2	CO2 Transport	6
3.3	CO2 Storage.....	7
3.4	Cross-cutting.....	7
4	scientific areas to prioritise in Horizon Europe	9
5	Messages for the future of the programme.....	10
	APPENDIX EERA JP CCS R&I recommendations for CO2 capture, transport and storage per June 2023 ...	11

1 INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 2.1 Recommendations on CCUS R&I priorities for Horizon Europe work programme.

1.1 Background

Strong continued support for CCS and CCU research and innovation (R&I) through the Horizon Europe and partnerships is crucial, and the EU and national funding programs should be coordinated and coherent.

The project – ZEP and the IWG9 – is actively supporting the development of the Horizon Europe work programmes. Together with the European Energy Research Alliance (EERA) the project has given input to the European Commission, responding to the consultation “Past, present and future of the Horizon R&I programmes 2014-2027”.

2 THE IMPORTANCE OF CCS AND CCU TECHNOLOGIES AND R&I

The at-scale deployment of Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS), Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU) and low-carbon hydrogen, along with the supporting transport and storage infrastructure, is essential for the decarbonisation of the European Union (EU) industrial and power sectors and to deliver negative emissions. The accelerated deployment of these solutions will thus support the achievement of the EU net-zero and net-negative ambitions, as outlined in the European Green Deal and the European Climate Law.

A favourable investment framework is necessary to support these technologies along the innovation cycle – from R&I to commercialisation. The Horizon programme and the Innovation Fund have been instrumental in driving the development of these technologies. We also welcome the new Horizon Europe Work programme for 2023-2024 which includes calls for R&I activities on CCS and CCU, including carbon removals and transport and storage demonstration projects.

Below we highlight priority areas for CCUS Research and Innovation (R&I) activities. Collaboration, knowledge sharing and coordinated calls at the regional, national and EU levels should be fostered to fully explore the potential of EU funding programmes. In addition, synergies with other EU programmes (e.g., Innovation Fund, Connecting Europe Facility, Important Projects of Common European Interest, Projects of Common/Mutual Interest) should be explored so that priority areas for R&I can be better tailored to commercial applications.

3 KEY R&I SOLUTIONS TO SUPPORT CCS/CCU DEPLOYMENT AND SCALE UP

CCS and CCU applications, as well as CO₂ infrastructure, are deployable today and already operational in Europe, although not at scale. Some challenges remain, where further R&I is needed. The following subchapters outline the recommended focus areas for the CCS/CCU value chain. See also in Appendix for more details and context.

3.1 CO₂ Capture

- Flexible capture systems
- Compactness, modularization, hybrid systems, heat integration, process intensification
- Cost effective capture systems (CAPEX and OPEX)
- Cost-effective materials
- High capture rates (>95%)
- CDR schemes
- Integrated capture systems for industry clusters, including multi-user capabilities
- Next generation novel reactor designs
- Control of emissions and other HSE considerations
- Funnel of projects at different TRL
- Targeted fundamental research

See also this deliverable from the Impacts9-project [D3.4 Recommendations on the steps required to deliver R&I activity 6: Developing next generation CO₂ capture technologies](#)

3.2 CO₂ Transport

- Developing the knowledge basis on the impact of CO₂ composition and impurities – to support emitters and the development of sufficiently flexible quality specifications for CO₂ transport and storage projects. This can also inform the development of Europe-wide CO₂ specifications, with the view of supporting a cross-border, interoperable transport network.
- Flow metering on an accuracy level suitable for taxation / custody transfer (< 1% ?)
- Developing international standards / guidelines for CO₂ quality and further assessment of the various effects of impurities
- Engineering approaches for pipeline (and various other elements of the grid) safety and operability
- Technical and economic analysis of interfaces to capture and storage (whole chain optimization, effect of changes in models)
- Dynamic simulation and control of complex CO₂ networks

- Interoperability of shipping (including CCS on ships)
- Regulatory framework and public participation
- Building, operating and managing complex transport networks,

3.3 CO₂ Storage

- CCS solutions for remote emitters (e.g., combine CO₂ storage and geothermal systems)
- Effective and efficient monitoring strategies,
- Develop solutions for long-term risks (e.g., EU or national trust funds),
- Develop methods for site conformance monitoring and assessment,
- Develop performance standards for storage projects, supporting storage development and avoiding creating unnecessary barriers,
- Explore solutions for legacy wells, namely their cost-effective reparation, and techniques for their examinations and characterisation,
- Speed up CO₂ storage development and decreasing the time it takes for a storage site to get to permitting stage (e.g., funding to explore potential storage sites),
- Map storage capacity in Europe – a Europe-wide storage atlas will support strategic planning. It is recommended to leverage on the experience of Member States that have developed national storage maps. The use of big data and artificial intelligence applications can also be explored for this purpose. The functionalities and benefits of the Atlas is further explored in the IWG9 report [‘Recommendations on the Steps to establish a R&I Activity 4 European Storage Atlas’](#),
- Support to pre-commercial CO₂ geological storage appraisal activities, to speed up storage site (commercial) development, to support planning of CO₂ capture projects (and related source to store linkages), and help closing the storage capacity gap. This is further explored in the IWG9 report [‘Unlocking European CO₂ Storage Capacity’](#).
- Updates of these recommendations will be provided to the European Commission, DG RTD in the coming months related to a regular dialogue set up over many years between EERA JP CCS and ETIP ZEP Network Technology (NWT) on one hand and DG RTD on the other hand.

3.4 Cross-cutting

- Capacity building of competent authorities / regulators
- Map supply chains of CCS and CCU applications, identifying the sourcing of key materials and forecasting demand,
- Metering, supporting the identification of biogenic and fossil CO₂ streams,
- Social acceptance of CCS and CCU solutions,

- Harmonisation of life cycle assessment (LCA) and sustainability assessment for the use of biomass (e.g., in Bioenergy with CCS applications).

4 SCIENTIFIC AREAS TO PRIORITISE IN HORIZON EUROPE

The transition to net-zero and, subsequently, net-negative emissions will require a portfolio of technologies, including CCS and CCU. Below are recommended areas in the CCS/CCU space:

- CCS for industry: adaption of current capture methods to new areas, development and deployment of higher Technology Readiness Level (TRL) capture, and cost reduction,
- CCS for flexible power generation,
- The role/scale of different CCU applications,
- Low-carbon hydrogen: the role of CCS-enabled low-carbon hydrogen in meeting early demand and scaling up the hydrogen market,
- The role/scale of engineered carbon removal solutions (i.e., Bioenergy with CCS and Direct Air Capture), e.g., definition/volumes of residual emissions,
- The required CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure to link source to store, including the development of a Europe-wide storage market to broaden the choice of storage sites,
- Collaboration initiatives, such as the SET Plan Implementation working groups, which bring together key actors – from industry, R&I, governments, and the European Commission. Such collaboration initiatives achieve high impact, speed up innovation cycles, and strengthen the coupling of national, regional and supra-national approaches.

5 MESSAGES FOR THE FUTURE OF THE PROGRAMME

The industrial scale CCS and CCU projects are expected to generate new knowledge and to encounter areas where further research is needed. For this reason, synergies between EU-supported projects at different stages of the innovation cycle should be explored. By establishing feedback loops and effective communication channels, R&I projects will be able to better address industrial challenges of high-TRL projects and benefit from the knowledge created at an industrial scale. With this in mind, we welcome the European Commission's proposal to review the Innovation Fund Delegated Act, with a strengthened governance aiming to create synergies between the Innovation Fund and Horizon Europe.

In addition, the Horizon Europe model and process can hinder its attractiveness among CCS project developers – notably, the evaluation process takes long and has an uncertain result which creates unnecessary delays for R&I projects. In this context, it is important to explore options to increase chances of application success by setting up clear requirements and to expedite evaluation process.

APPENDIX EERA JP CCS R&I RECOMMENDATIONS FOR CO₂ CAPTURE, TRANSPORT AND STORAGE PER JUNE 2023

Three documents:

- EERA JP CCS: “Interoperable CO₂-Transport Networks – Towards a European Network Code for CO₂ Transport”, Roland Span, 2023-04-14
- “What next for CO₂ storage research? How understanding was gained from stakeholder consultation whilst developing the Science Case for a UK CO₂ Storage Research Facility (CSRF)”, Jim White, British Geological Survey
- EERA JP CCS: “What’s next for CO₂ capture research?”, Marie Bysveen, EERA JP CCS Programme director, SINTEF, 2023-06-09